

COMPREHENSIVE DEVELOPMENT OF PARKS FOR HISTORICAL AND CULTURAL EVENTS

Pardayev Abbas

Teacher at Karshi State University

Pardayeva Mukhlisa

Student at Karshi State University

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ABSTRACT

This article examines the definition of the historical reenactment movement. It provides an overview of well-known Russian historical reenactment parks. Recommendations are provided for the comprehensive design of parks for festivals and year-round visits to explore the country's history.

Historical reenactment is an educational or recreational activity in which people recreate, according to a plan, individual aspects of a historical event or period [1]. This could be a specific moment of a battle, such as the Kutuzov offensive during the Battle of Kursk, or an entire event, such as the Battle of Kulikovo. Reenactment involves the accurate recreation of clothing, weapons, armor, household utensils, jewelry, etc., based on scientific data and in accordance with historical technologies and materials of the era being reconstructed.

Currently, the reconstruction of historical events as a tourist destination

The development of patriotic business can be seen as one of the ways to improve the patriotic education of teenagers and young people, drawing their attention to the history and culture of their country through leisure activities.

The historical reenactment movement is a unique phenomenon that intertwines many activities, including science, art, military affairs, sports, and tourism. Reenacting historical events is gaining increasing popularity each year, becoming a form of international cultural cooperation. Thanks to the historical reenactment movement, attention to cultural heritage is growing, new dynamic forms of its actualization are emerging, and original methods of educational work with children and young people are emerging [2].

It's now safe to say that an entire industry has developed in this field, encompassing historians, tailors, and gunsmiths. In most countries, legislation permits the purchase of weapons required for the festival. There are numerous companies worldwide that produce reenactment supplies. Besides promoting the popularization of a country's history, this activity is also economically beneficial, generating additional revenue for the state treasury. In Russia, the sale of such weapons is prohibited.

However, historical reenactment is currently only seasonal due to our country's climate. Therefore, to develop this trend, it is necessary to create comprehensive open-air historical

museums and living history parks. These attract tourists and provide opportunities to study the historical heritage of a given area, learn crafts, develop experimental archaeology, promote family leisure, create discussion platforms, and attract investment to the region.

An example of such a successful project is the Bastion Historical Park, a cultural and educational center in the "living history" format located in Karelia, whose main goal is to foster interest in the study of Russian history. The park features atmospheric locations that closely resemble the era—from an early medieval fortress to a 20th-century military unit. The park offers themed tours that immerse you in the era, as well as engaging workshops where anyone can try their hand at being a medieval craftsman and make their own souvenir.

Another example is the Rusborg Historical and Cultural Center in the Lipetsk Region. Rusborg is a life-size fortress from the Early Middle Ages, built for the study and public display of reconstructed objects and structures from the 9th-11th centuries of Ancient Rus'. The park consists of a complex of unique objects and interactive museum sites representing northern, southern, and European Russian architecture. Currently, the park hosts three military-historical reenactment festivals—Rusborg, Ladeinoe Pole, and Strelets—which have won the hearts of regular participants and spectators from across Russia, for whom trips to these festivals have long become family events [3].

At the same time, the historical reenactment movement in Russia has promising prospects, reflecting increased tourist traffic, a positive impact on regional development, and the patriotic education of the younger generation. Participating in a reenacted historical event allows tourists to feel like "heroes of the past" and gain a better understanding of the history of a particular region and its unique characteristics.

Currently, the movement of historical reconstruction of the Early Middle Ages has about 50,000 people in all regions

Therefore, in the near future, there is a need to build unified, permanent complexes with permanent structures and sets dedicated to housing construction and the country's history, while fully preserving the construction technology. These structures and sets include the palisade and dwellings with their associated household items.

Housing construction zones are historical replicas of the main types of dwellings: dugouts, semi-dugouts, log cabins, and sheds.

The facilities should reconstruct the everyday life of the corresponding era. Workshops (sewing, pottery, blacksmithing, etc.), demonstrations, and events can be held in the areas using the facilities. Since the park will be open year-round, safe and comfortable access for all types of vehicles must be provided via a paved road.

Festivals that last several days attract people from all over the country, so they need to be provided with accommodation and food. This requires taverns that can accommodate large crowds. To accommodate participants and spectators, the park grounds must provide space for tents and marquees.

Additionally, the site must include space for stands where reenactors will hold battles. The complex should also include recreational areas with gazebos, children's playgrounds, beaches (if available), and walking paths.

The park also needs to accommodate an administrative building that will regulate the operation of the entire park.

When designing, it is also important to take into account the requirements for accessible visits to the park for people with limited mobility.

Public spaces should contribute to the architectural and artistic expressiveness of the city and be a comfortable and accessible environment for recreation.

Thus, historical reenactment attracts more and more people to study the history of their region, providing entertainment and recreation for tourists, who acquire new skills and knowledge. It also fosters a caring attitude toward nature and the cultural heritage of their country. Therefore, it is so important to develop and create such "living history" parks today.

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